

Advanced Materials and Processes for Large, Lightweight, Space-Based Mirrors

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Abstract—The use of monolithic glass to produce large, rigid segmented members for lightweight space-based mirror systems has reached its limit due to the long lead times, high processing costs, and launch load/weight requirements. New material solutions and manufacturing processes are required to meet the Air Force’s directed energy weapons, reconnaissance/surveillance, and secured communication needs. Mirror structural substrates made out of advanced composite materials (metal, ceramic, and polymer), foams, or microsphere arrays should allow for CTE and modulus tailorability, low-density, and high strength, stiffness, and toughness. Due to the multi-phase complexities of these new systems, mechanical polishing to visual specifications for figure and surface finish roughness requirements will be difficult. New methods of replication and sol-gel or polymer spinning will be required to produce the required optical finishes. In this paper selected material and process solutions will be discussed.¹

these applications, mass, size, natural frequency, and reliability are major issues due to flight/launch constraints and anticipated life times. Cost, production infrastructure, and scheduling also become important technology drivers in some missions where high acreage is needed. For example, a primary mirror for an airborne directed energy system could consist of a monolithic design with a diameter of up to 1.5 meters to fit inside existing airframes. In this case the mirror is shielded or encased within the airframe so fracture toughness of the mirror may not be a major issue. Therefore, the current lightweight glass mirror technology might suffice [Ref. 1] and then the technology driver for this application may be U.S. corporate sustainment since only 10 to 20 systems would be fielded.

In contrast, a space based directed energy system would require a constellation of very large mirrors, 10 to 15 meters in diameter. They would have to be a segmented design with segments no larger than about 3.25 meters so that they could be stowed in the Space Shuttle cargo bay or launch vehicle shrouds. Once launched to proper orbit these segments would have to be assembled or deployed in space. To meet the launch payload weight constraints, the mirror would also have to be substantially lightweighted to an aerial density of less than 15 kg/m². Their reliability and robustness is a major concern because they will be un-shielded and exposed to the high launch loads, in-space assembly damage, and micrometer impacts. Here monolithic glass mirrors may not be able meet these requirements and advanced mirror materials and advanced process designs may have to be sought. For this space based application production capability of approximately five to seven 10-meter diameter, segmented, primary mirrors/year would be required for a period of up to 15 or 20 years. Unfortunately, the infrastructure does not currently exist in the U.S. to meet such a large production quantity. Therefore, substantial government and corporate investment would be required to meet this goal. Some of this infrastructure investment may be shared by NASA if the mirrors can be cooled to cryogenic temperatures without increasing its figure or finish distortions. They would be employed in systems such as the James Webb Space Telescope (Fig. 1) being constructed to replace the Hubble Space Telescope.

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1. THE NEED FOR ADVANCED MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Department of Defense (DoD), National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), and other U.S. Government agencies have identified airborne and space-based systems that will require mirrors ranging in size from 0.1 to 100 meters in diameter. Large, lightweight, high precision mirrors are critical for enhanced surveillance/reconnaissance missions, directed energy weapons and communication systems, laser radar systems, X-ray and UV telescopes, as well as large astronomical telescopes. In all of

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Fig. 1 James Webb Space Telescope being constructed to replace the Hubble Space Telescope. Image courtesy of Northrop Grumman

2. CURRENT MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Monolithic Glass Mirrors

Silica-based glasses have been used for hundreds of years as both the optical and structural substrate for mirrors. It makes a good optical substrate due to its low softening point, low hardness, and its absence of a grain structure. This allows it to be formed, ground, and polished into complex shapes with precise figure ($\cong \lambda/20$ RMS) and very smooth surface finish down to a minimum of $\cong 3 \text{ \AA}$ RMS. Once the figure and finish requirements are met for the particular application, then, it is coated with a very thin metal film to obtain the mirrors reflective characteristics.

Unfortunately, glass makes a poor structural substrate due to its low modulus, tensile strength, and fracture toughness. To overcome these shortcomings, thick and heavy mirror designs have been used along with good handling and mounting practices. Reliability and robustness was assured in space-based systems by encasement of the mirror system into metallic tube structures. However, in future airborne and space-based mirror systems where weight and size are constrained by the payload requirements; this shielded approach and high aerial density design may not be feasible. Non-shielded, low aerial density designs may be required to meet the system goals and robustness has to be provided by either new structural substrate materials with high modulus, strength, and fracture toughness or with new hybrid designs.

Another benefit for using glass in mirror designs is that its amorphous structure allows for a wide variation in chemistries. This has been used to adjust the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) to values approaching zero at various use temperatures. These mirror glasses provide dimensional stability of the mirror figure with respect to the thermal variations of the environment. A brief review of glass chemistry shows how this was made possible.

Silica-based glass is an inorganic material with a metastable amorphous structure (no long range order). Most glasses are produced by supercooling their liquids to a rigid condition without crystallization. Some glasses are prepared without cooling from the liquid state such as vapor grown or solution grown glasses. In either class, the atoms of a silicate glass form a continuous framework of silicon-oxygen tetrahedral bonded together at their corners. The bonds are strong but they have a large variation in the Si-O-Si bond angle. Such a random network is not necessarily uniform and local variations in density and structure are to be expected. This variability in local density and bond angle allows the absorption of thermally induced vibrational energy through transverse modes of vibration and the adjustment of bond angles. This results in a low coefficient of thermal expansion.

For example, fused silica (SiO_2), commonly referred to as fused quartz or vitreous silica, has a thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) of $0.55 \text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ at 300°K (Table 1). This can be reduced to $0.02 \text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ at 300°K by alloying with a small addition (7% by weight) of titania (TiO_2). Corning Glass produces this glass composition by a vapor growth process and refers to it as Ultra Low Expansion (ULE) glass [Ref. 2], (Table 1). MSNW Inc. of San Marcos CA. under Air Force sponsorship has recently produced this composition by a sol-gel approach [Ref. 3].

The CTE of a glass can also be tailored by the homogeneous precipitation of negative CTE crystalline phases throughout the glass matrices. This is the case of Zerodur glass from Schott Glass [Ref. 4], which is a glass-ceramic system containing Li_2O , Al_2O_3 , and SiO_2 (LAS) with a small amount of TiO_2 . In this glass, Al_2O_3 suppresses the formation of a miscibility gap so that the modifier (Li_2O) can be added in high concentrations and TiO_2 is used as a nucleation agent. Annealing LAS glass at moderate temperatures results in the homogeneous precipitation of a highly anisotropic eucryptite phase $\text{Li}_2\text{O} - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 - 2 \text{SiO}_2$ onto the network sites containing titanium ions. One axis of the eucryptite phase has a large negative CTE, which compensates for the positive CTE of the glass matrix, resulting in a net CTE of $0.05 \text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ at 300°K .

ULE and Zerodur both can show dimensional instability if segregation of the elements occurs during processing of large boules, resulting in non-homogeneous dispersion of the alloying elements or the negative CTE phase. Polishing and print-through distortions may also become a problem for high-resolution mirrors if the crystalline phase is allowed to grow much larger than 200 nm . As with all glasses, both materials suffer from very low thermal conductivity, strength, modulus, and fracture toughness. Therefore, although glass is a good optical member because it can be polished to a complicated figure and a very smooth surface finish, it is a poor structural member and for some applications it may not be the best choice for a mirror.

2.2 *Lightweighting Monolithic Glass Mirrors*

Significant effort has been made over the past twenty years to reduce the weight of airborne and space-based glass mirrors. These efforts were driven by needs to reduce launch costs, to decrease the thermal mass in order to equilibrate temperatures in shorter times, and to minimize the weight and complexity of the support and handling equipment.

The Hubble Space Telescope mirror was a lightweight design fabricated by Perkin-Elmer (now Goodrich) in Danbury, CN [Ref. 5]. This mirror was produced using a frit bonding process to join individual ULE glass plates to create an open-faced honeycombed core structure. The core was then frit bonded between two ULE glass face-sheets to produce a lightweight mirror blank. The mirror blank was ground, polished, and vapor coated with aluminum to create a visible light reflective surface. This mirror was 2.4m (8ft) in diameter and weighed 828 kg (1820 lbs.). It had an areal density of approximately 200 kg/m². The major problems encountered in building this mirror were thermal distortions and uneven stresses in the plates and joints. Additionally, this processing method was extremely labor intensive, time-consuming, and expensive.

Over the past thirty years many efforts have been conducted at numerous places to overcome the processing difficulties experienced in building the Hubble mirror and to develop methods/processes to substantially reduce the areal density below that of the Hubble mirror. Most recently, the Advanced Mirror Systems Demonstrator (AMSD) program, a jointly funded effort by the AF, NASA, and the NRO, (program ran by NASA MSFC) provides a good reference for the state-of-the-art large, lightweight mirrors [Ref. 5, 6].

In this program, Eastman Kodak Co. used an abrasive water jet (AWJ) milling technique to fabricate thin walled, open-ended, honeycomb core structure out of bulk ULE glass (Fig. 2). They then used a low temperature fusion bonding process to attach the front and back faceplates producing a honeycomb sandwich type design. A 1.4-meter wide hexagonal mirror segment is shown in Figure 3. This lightweighted glass mirror segment was then attached to a carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composite reaction structure with 16 actuators. This total mirror system has an areal density of about 12 kg/m².

Goodrich Inc. produced a 1.3-meter wide, hexagonal shaped, fused silica mirror segment with an open-back honeycomb design using AWJ milling [Ref 5, 6], (Fig 4). This mirror was attached to a carbon reinforced polymer matrix composite reaction structure using 37 actuators. This total system had an areal density of about 15 kg/m².

Both of these glass mirror manufacturers were very successful in reducing the areal density of their mirror systems into the range of 15 kg/m². However, both contractors appear to have reached the lower limit in areal

density that one can expect for a monolithic glass mirror. Any additional reductions would have to come through hybrid material approaches, new materials, or composites. These AMSD contractors were also very successful in reducing the cost and fabrication time of a glass mirror to half that of a comparable Hubble mirror.

Fig. 2. Kodak's ULE Honeycomb Core produced by AWJ milling in the AMSD program.

Fig. 3 Kodak's lightweighted glass mirror segment produced in the AMSD program. (1.4m)

Fig.4 The Goodrich lightweighted glass mirror segment produced in the AMSD program. (1.3m)

2.3 Glass Ceramic Composite Mirrors

In the 1980's, the Air Force and NASA sponsored numerous research projects at United Technologies Research Center to produce carbon fiber reinforced borosilicate glass matrix composites called COMGLAS. These composites were fabricated in both continuous and discontinuous fiber forms. Since the T-300 graphite fibers has a negative CTE in its axial dimension, the composites CTE could be tailored to near zero values with the appropriate fiber volume fraction and orientation (Fig.5). Additionally, fibrous reinforcements decreased the density (2 g/cc compared to the glass alone at 2.2 g/cc) and increased the modulus (168GPa compared to the glass alone at 67 GPa), the tensile strength (600 MPa compared to the glass alone at 100 MPa), and the fracture toughness (22 MPa $m^{0.5}$ compared to glass alone at 0.77 MPa $m^{0.5}$) {Table 1}, [Ref. 7-10]. High toughness was produced by the formation of a thin turbostratic carbon layer between the fiber and the glass. This carbon layer was soft and allowed for crack deflection at the fiber interface instead of crack propagation through the fiber. The toughness of the composites was then increased due to the fiber pullout mechanism, which hampers crack growth in the glass phase. *High fracture toughness will be needed in unprotected mirror structures that may experience micro-meteor impacts or large structures that must be assembled in space where part-handling collisions are to be expected.* United Technologies produced small chopped fiber-reinforced glass mirrors (referred to as TSC mirrors) as demonstration articles with areal density below 10kg/m². Unfortunately, the as-molded surface roughness was high (1000 A RMS) and polishing these three phase composite systems (C_{fiber} + C_{interface layer} + glass_{matrix}) to an acceptable finish was difficult. The technology for over coating or cladding the surface with a dense, near zero CTE glass, followed by polishing to the visual range was not successful at that time due to poor sol-gel chemistry formulations (Fig. 6). Revisiting this concept today with advanced sol-gel coating and cladding technology will be difficult because United Technologies stopped all COMGLAS work about ten years ago and no other organizations have continued this work.

Fig 5. CTE of C/glass CMC mirror material called COMGLAS by UTRC.

Fig 6. Small C/glass COMGLAS mirrors by UTRC.

It is important to point out that this was one of the first attempts at tailoring the CTE of a ceramic mirror substrate by fibrous compositing. It also provided large increases in strength, modulus, and fracture toughness; all, which are beneficial to large lightweight, mirror designs. Unfortunately, the surface figure and finish issues could not be resolved at that time but should be revisited with today's coating technologies. This work and work of others showed some guidelines that need to be addressed if fibrous composite are going to be revisited. Fibrous composite for mirror substrates are complicated systems because one has to obtain near uniform volume fraction (matrix, reinforcement, and porosity) as measured in the through thickness direction to avoid print through type distortions. Additionally, the fiber architecture needs to be at least two-dimensionally random in the plane of the mirror. The larger these deviate from the desired conditions, the more problems one will encounter with fiber print through distortions caused by either mechanical polishing (a modulus and hardness mismatch effect) and/or thermal excursions seen during the coating process and the operational range (a CTE and thermal conductivity mismatch effect).

In the case of discontinuous fiber reinforced matrix composites where hot working (flow) is often used to consolidate the fiber/matrix preform and then to form a near-net-shaped by flowing the mixture into a mold cavity; stable processing conditions and good flow designs are needed to avoid excessive fiber re-alignment and fiber pile-ups [Ref. 11]. Both of these defects will contribute to non-uniform CTE behavior and their occurrence is expected to increase with the complexity of the mold and the size of the mirror. These types of defects can be minimized using processes where the fiber architecture is rigidized in a mold prior to infiltration by a very low viscosity matrix material (either glass, metal, or polymer). In continuous fiber reinforced matrix composites, the fiber tows are either laid up then infiltrated with molten glass or they are pulled through a glass sol and these sol-infiltrated tows are laid up and pressed. In either case, fiber agglomeration can be an issue. So, fiber preform architecture and lay-up issues need to be properly addressed to avoid distortion and warping issues.

Long-term dimensional stability is another issue that needs to be addressed for composites. In the past, matrix creep was observed in polymer matrix composites due to localized

overloading in the matrix phase that resulted in chemical changes and/or cross linking of the polymer. In either case the deformation was not reversible and this leads to permanent distortions in the mirrors. Higher strength polymers and better composite lay-up methods of today should help overcome these issues. Creep has also been an issue with metals and metal matrix composites due to dislocation migration and entanglement during fabrication and actuation. Entanglement does not allow strains to be recovered upon unloading, resulting in permanent deformation of the mirror. This can be overcome in most metallic and metal matrix composites systems by saturating the metallic phases with dislocation networks through cryocycling prior to machining. Followed by polishing the surface to obtain the desired figure and finish. Dimensional stability has also been an issue in ceramic matrix composites due to the propagation of microcracks from porous areas. Composites such as C/SiC or SiC/SiC are often fabricated by vapor processing using Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI) and this typically leaves porous regions inside the composite due to enhanced deposition at the preform surface and depleted deposition rates in the interior. These composites can become overloaded at the local level causing microcrack generation and propagation in the matrix phase or along the fiber matrix interface. The stress at which this occurs is commonly referred to as the first matrix cracking stress and is observed through acoustic emission. The first matrix cracking stress can be drastically increased by fabricating higher density composites through either better CVI process controls or by infiltrating partially densified CMC's with liquid metals such as siliconized-SiC/SiC.

3.0 NEW MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

3.1 Lightweight Glass Mirrors: Sols and Spheres Arrays

The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL/ML) is sponsoring research at MSNW Inc. in CA to create near zero CTE glass sols for use as bonding agents, surface coatings and claddings. Additionally, they are fabricating near zero CTE glass micro-spheres and micro-balloons (Fig.7). Lightweighted glass mirrors will be fabricated by bonding ULE glass face-sheets to micro-balloon arrays. This mirror design should result in low areal density mirrors that are more robust than current honeycomb web designs. A micro-sphere array mirror would eliminate or minimize the quilting distortions due to the large web spacing needed for AWJ machining in current monolithic glass mirrors discussed previously. Additionally, a micro-sphere array mirror should eliminate the continuous crack path at the web-facesheet joints. It is often this joint where crack initiation starts and propagates catastrophically through the glass structure. The sol-gel chemistry approaches could also allow for the incorporation of nano-particles or nano-fibers to increase the tensile strength, modulus, and fracture toughness of the glass. Sols could also be used to build up glass claddings on glass ceramic composite mirrors or mirrors made of other materials. Near zero CTE glass micro-spheres and micro-balloons could also be used for

CTE control and strengtheners for polymer-based composites.

Fig.7 Near Zero CTE glass spheres produced by MSNW Inc.

3.2 Silicon Carbide-Based Mirrors

Silicon Carbide (SiC)-based materials are promising for use as structural substrates for large mirrors because of their high specific stiffness (high modulus and low density) and their low thermal distortion susceptibility (low thermal expansion and high thermal conductivity) (Fig. 8){Table 1}. However, there are many different types of SiC-based materials and each will polish differently producing variability in surface figure and finish, which is quoted throughout the literature. This variability comes from the differences in hardness and modulus between the phases present, their crystallography, and morphology.

In the following discussion, the materials and processes that produce the best surface finish using standard glass grinding and polishing procedures is presented first, followed by the next best material. It is important to note that the CTE of all the grades/types of SiC range from about 2-4 ppm/°C so actuation of the mirror might be required to hold a precise prescription of the optic if thermal cycling occurs during use.

Fig. 8 A comparison of three relevant parameters for a variety of mirror substrate candidate materials. Fracture toughness is in MPa^{0.5}, specific stiffness is in units of GPa-cc/gm, and thermal stability (=k/α), is in units of W/m-ppm. Data found in Table 1.

In general, pure SiC can be grouped into two crystalline forms: 1) alpha (α -SiC), which has a rhombohedral or hexagonal structure and is produced when the formation or processing temperature exceeds 2000°C and 2) beta (β -SiC), which is the face-centered cubic phase that is formed by processes that occur below 2000°C. The best surface finish for crystalline SiC would be expected from a dense, fine equiaxed grain-sized, single-phase, β -cubic structure because its hardness, strength, modulus, and thermal expansion behavior should be isotropic and the grain shape equiaxed. The highest density, smallest grain size, single-phase β -SiC is produced by controlled re-nucleation in a Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) process. In CVD-SiC, nucleation and growth occurs on a carbon mandrel at low temperatures (1200-1300°C) by the decomposition of MTS (*MethylTrichloroSilane*) according to the following reaction:

The process is conducted in a controlled atmosphere furnace chamber using many different processing conditions, both equilibrium and non-equilibrium depending upon the vendor. The resultant grain size and grain shape depend upon the conditions employed. Unfortunately, a large infrastructure investment in the reaction chamber is needed to produce large, dense β -SiC mirrors through the CVD process. Further, the deposition rates are rather slow, so schedule and cost are issues. Therefore, CVD β -SiC is mainly used for depositing thick coatings or claddings (the optical substrate) onto less expensive, less dense, sintered or siliconized SiC based materials (the structural substrate). The polishability of CVD β -SiC cladding material is limited by its high hardness. Too high a pressure on the polishing tool causes quilting type print through effects on lightweighted structures, while too low a pressure increases the polishing time making it uneconomical. The wavefront figure error measured by interferometry after standard polishing is on the order of 123nm RMS ($\lambda/5$ for 633nm) on an 8-inch (200mm) diameter mirror [Ref.12]. Fine polishing lowered this to 35nm ($\lambda/18$ for 633nm) and ion-beam polishing (IBP) further reduced the local figure error to 1.8nm RMS ($\lambda/100$ for 633nm) [Ref. 13].

Sintering of pure alpha (α -SiC) particles to full density is difficult unless both sub-micron powders and sintering aids are used. Powders and binders are usually mixed into a green body and isostatically pressed at room temperature into a blank. The green body can then be machined into an oversized geometry that is predicted by sintering shrinkage models. The oversized, machined green body part is then sintered above 2100°C resulting in approximately 17% linear shrinkage. The sintered SiC component is approximately 97% dense and contains 98 to 99% α -SiC depending upon the amount of sintering aids used. The sintered SiC produced by Boostec in France [Ref. 14] has a morphology consisting of 5 μm grain size with 3% porosity showing up as 1 to 2 μm voids along particle boundaries. The modulus is around 450 GPa as compared to 380GPa for

reaction bonded SiC or 250GPa for C/SiC composites. The bend strength was 374MPa compared to Zerodur glass at 10MPa and the fracture toughness is 2.8 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ compared to 0.9 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ for Zerodur glass. Astrium-Boostec has produced a 1.3m-sintered SiC demonstration mirror for the First near-IR telescope (Fig.9) [Ref. 15].

Fig. 9. Astrium-Boostec sintered SiC mirror (1.36m)

The Boostec sintered (α -SiC) has a surface roughness of about 0.5 μm as produced, ground to below 0.1 μm , and standard polished to 123nm RMS. For optic applications at shorter wavelengths, the sintered SiC 100 material is coated with CVD SiC and the ground, polished, and ion beamed plasma etched as previously discussed. The Boostec sintered (α -SiC) technology has recently been acquired in the USA by Coors Tek in Bolder, Colorado [Ref. 16].

Two-phased, siliconized-SiC is produced by several methods. The first method use slip cast (α -SiC) powders followed by sintering until they are approximately 60 to 80% dense. This preform is then infiltration with silicon metal by either gas phase deposition or liquid infiltration to fill the open porosity. Both methods produce a two-phased (SiC+Si) continuous structure that is intertwined. The latter process is used by Xinetics in Devens, MA to produce siliconized α -SiC mirrors [Ref. 17-18], (Fig. 10).

Fig 10. Siliconized SiC mirror from Xinetics Inc (0.5m).

The second method involves slip casting SiC with carbon particulates in a polymer binder that decomposes to a carbon network upon vacuum calcination. The calcined SiC/C body is then exposed to either Si vapor or molten Si to convert the carbon phase to SiC through a reaction bonding process. Any remaining porosity is then filled with silicon metal. This method is used by several vendors including M-Cubed Technologies in CT and SSG Inc. in MA to produce mirror substrates and optical support components. Some mechanical and thermal properties of these siliconized-SiC's are listed in Table 1. The polishability of the siliconized-SiC material depends upon the phase size (typically around 30 μ m SiC) and volume fraction (typically around 70% SiC), but ballpark numbers for figure are around 63nm ($\lambda/10$ RMS for $\lambda=633$ nm) and finish of 2.1nm ($\lambda/300$ RMS for $\lambda=633$ nm)[Ref. 17]. As previously mentioned, better figure and finish are obtainable on these SiC-based mirrors if a high density, fine grain-sized CVD β -SiC cladding is deposited and polished. Additionally, PVD silicon cladding can also be used since it will form a good integral bond with the silicon in the two-phase substrate. PVD silicon claddings can be polished by standard polishing methods to about the same values that CVD β -SiC obtains when ion beam polished.

3.3 What's new in lightweight SiC-based mirror- new processes and composites

Poco Graphite produces lightweighted, near net shaped β -SiC mirrors by taking a special grade of graphite and machining it to the desired structure followed by conversion of the graphite to silicon carbide through a gas phase reaction. This reaction process has a very small but predictable dimensional change. The as-converted β -SiC structure has approximately 20% porosity. Property data for Poco's β -SiC material can be found in Table 1. This mirror substrate is then cladded with CVD β -SiC to make a 100% β -SiC mirror. This is then polished using conventional optical polishing techniques by Zygo to a roughness of 3.2A and figure 0.26 waves. The Poco/Zygo team also investigate magnetorheological finishing (MRF) and shown that this method reduces the polishing time and can provide a surface with a figure error of $\lambda/10$ and a surface finish of 1nm RMS. [Ref. 19, 20] Fig 11.

Fig. 11. Poco SiC mirror.

Many DOD and NASA organizations have sponsored numerous businesses to develop carbon and SiC fiber-reinforced SiC and siliconized SiC matrix composites. These ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) have been fabricated in both continuous and discontinuous fashion by numerous companies using a variety of processing routes. As in glass composites, carbon fiber reinforcements allow for CTE and strength tailorability, but polishability problems arise when a weak carbon interfacial coating is deposited on the fibers to promote crack deflection and improve fracture toughness. Polishability is improved by adding a thick cladding of dense CVD β -SiC to form an optical substrate. (Chopped C_{fiber}/C_{interface layer}/SiC_{matrix}) structural substrates can be fabricated by many processes. For example, AIBG and ECM from Germany, molds a mixture of SiC and C particles, polymer binder; and chopped carbon fibers (with and without an interfacial coatings) into blank. These are heat treated under vacuum to form a porous graphitized green body. The green body is easily machined into a lightweighted shape using standard CNC milling equipment. It is then infiltrated under vacuum with liquid silicon to form a C/SiC composite structure. [Ref. 20, 21], (Fig 12). It is claimed that there is no noticeable shrinkage in the infiltration/conversion process and virtually no residual stress left in the mirror. The composite is then rough ground and cladded with slurry to form a SiC+Si surface layer that is polished to a surface roughness of 2nm.

Fig. 12. The back side of the 500mm AIBG-ECM C/SiC mirror with an areal density of 8kg/m².

Continuous fiber reinforced CMC's such as C/SiC and SiC/SiC have been fabricated by CVI by numerous vendors. As stated previously, there are many variations of the CVI process some equilibrium process while others are non-equilibrium processes. For example, General Electric/Honeywell has very large reactors that use an isothermal equilibrium process. The process is extremely slow (taking months) and often requires the part to be machined intermittently. However, their reactors are very large, so small parts can be done in large batches to

economize the process. In contrast, Ceracom Inc. in MA and Oak Ridge National Lab in TN use non-equilibrium CVI processes. These require component specific designs of reactors, which direct and speed up the deposition process (taking hours to days). Unfortunately, only one part can be infiltrated at a time and new furnace inserts (made of graphite) usually have to be constructed or re-surfaced after each run. The cost and processing times for both CMCs can be reduced by deliberately densifying the composites to approximately 60% by CVI and then melt infiltrating with liquid Si to form a fully dense, siliconized-SiC/SiC composite. These composites are then clad with either CVD β -SiC, PVD Si, or melt replication with Si to form the optical substrate. The mechanical and thermal properties for the Ceracom Si-SiC/SiC composite is provided in Table 1 [Ref. 22] and a small mirror is shown in (Fig 13).

Fig. 13. Si-SiC/SiC CMC mirror from Ceracom (2inch)

The desirable features of CMC mirrors are that their CTEs and areal densities are low while their strength, modulus, and fracture toughness are high. High strength and fracture toughness will be needed for durability and robustness in unshielded space based mirror systems such as the James Webb Telescope and the Space Based Laser. These types of programs probably can't survive public scrutiny and absorbent cost overruns associated with a catastrophic failure of the primary mirror caused by handling, assembly accidents, or micrometeoroid impacts. Survivability and longevity requirements will demand fielded mirrors be made of highly durable and stable materials. Therefore, as a community we need to continue to invest in scaling up these composite mirrors to very large sizes while assuring thermal-mechanical stability.

3.4 Metallic Mirrors

Most metals, like aluminum and nickel, have been used as mirror materials in terrestrial applications for years because they are easily formed, machined, polished, handled, and are low cost. Additionally, most metals are highly reflective so they do not require coatings to yield high broadband reflectivity. Unfortunately, metals generally have high CTEs at ambient temperatures, which limits their applications.

However at cryogenic temperatures below 70°K, beryllium has a near zero CTE. This along with its low density (1.85g/cm^3), high stiffness (303Gpa) and cryogenic-thermal conductivity (195 Wm-K) make it a desirable mirror material for high-resolution infrared imaging where the mirror needs to be cryogenically cooled. Beryllium suffers from issues such as high cost, toxicity, slow machineability, and anisotropic behavior due to its hexagonal crystal structure. Processing by standard metallic hot working methods such as forging and rolling results in crystallographic texturing that cannot be homogenized through recrystallization. These textured grain structure results in an anisotropic modulus and thermal expansion behavior of the mirror substrate. Only powder processes such as hot isostatic pressing, vacuum hot pressing, sintering, or vacuum plasma spray will yield a randomly orientated grain structure that shows isotropic behavior. Beryllium, like most metallics, also has a micro plasticity problem at room temperature under high loads that may require a thermal cycling treatment to saturate and stabilize its dislocation microstructure. Nabarro-Herring and Coble creep of these low micro-yield strength metals may become a concern during handling and manufacturing. In the AMSD program Ball Aerospace Inc. has fabricated a Be mirror for evaluation at cryogenic temperatures (Fig 14) [Ref. 5, 23, 24]. Ball has not observed any creep at loads of 2 ksi over 2684hrs.

Fig. 14. Be mirror by Ball Aerospace produced for AMSD program (1.4 m)

As discussed in previous sections, several manufacturers have used polycrystalline silicon as a mirror cladding (optical substrate) and as a melt infiltrate for SiC and siliconized-SiC materials. Its isotropic behavior (diamond cubic structure), low density (2.3g/cm^3) and CTE ($2.5\text{ppm/K}@300\text{K}$), high thermal conductivity (148 W/m-K) and excellent polishability (finish surface roughness of 5 angstroms RMS) make it a good candidate for an optical substrate [Ref. 25]. Polycrystalline silicon can be fabricated using melt/solidification, sintering, plasma spraying, PVD, and CVD. Highly polishable (0.5 angstrom) single crystal Si from the electronics industry has also been used by Schaffer Corp. [Ref. 25] as an optical substrate material on a flat mirror, but it's size is limited to approximately 12 inches by

single crystal growth methods. Silicon has a low modulus and an affinity for atomic oxygen, which may limit its applicability for certain missions.

3.5 What's new in metallic mirrors—foam and composites?

An open cell foam structure can provide structural support to a dense facesheet without sagging, hence eliminating quilting figure distortions as seen in web-based mirror architectures. Foams also allow for substantial lowering of the weight of the mirror. Foams have been produced out of a variety of materials including aluminum, silicon, silicon carbide, and carbon. Silicon foam can be produced by several methods, including a displacement reaction between C foam and SiO vapor according to the following reaction: $\text{SiO}_g + \text{C}_{\text{foam}} = \text{Si}_{\text{foam}} + \text{CO}_g$ or by C diffusion through a CVD-Si surface coating that has been deposited onto C foam. Schaffer Corp [Ref. 24, 26] has used the latter process to convert machined C foam preforms to net-shaped Si foam preforms. The surface of the Si foam is then coated with Si particulate slurry or by CVD until the surface is closed off. A fully dense optical substrate is then applied by CVD-Si and polished to the appropriate figure and finish (Fig 15).

Fig. 15. Six-inch diameter Si foam mirror from Shaffer Inc.

Continuous and discontinuous carbon fiber-reinforced magnesium and aluminum matrix composites are currently being studied as possible mirror structural substrates by Metal Matrix Cast Composites in MA. [Ref. 24, 27, 28]. As previously mentioned, the volume fraction of carbon fibers can be used to tailor the net CTE in a composite material. It can also increase the strength, modulus, thermal conductivity, and fracture toughness of the base material. For example, a 55% by volume carbon-reinforced Mg alloy results in a net CTE of 2 ppm/K in-plane, a density of 2 g/cm³, a stiffness 102 GPa and a thermal conductivity of 180 W/mK; this compares well with Be (Fig. 8). It is anticipated that changing to a PAN-based fiber and thermal seasoning of the C/Mg MMC can increase the stiffness substantially. Additionally, carbon-reinforced Al and Mg matrix composites are highly machineable to a lightweight configuration without warpage. These structural substrates are then coated with a CVD-Si cladding

and polished to surface roughness of 10 angstroms RMS (Fig 16).

Fig. 16. Three inch diameter C/Al and C/Mg mirrors from MMCC

3.6 Carbon fibers and foams

Conventional carbon fibers display many unique properties that when, combined with a matrix, form composites of great interest to the mirror community. These fibers are commercially available with a tremendous variety of properties and prices. They range from approximately 5 μm to 10 μm in diameter. Tensile modulus varies from 200 GPa to nearly 600 GPa with strengths varying from 2.7 GPa to 6.3 GPa. Thermal conductivity can be higher than 1000 W/m°C. They are very robust in a space environment, and these fibers display coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) as low as -1.0 ppm/C. With diameters of 5 μm to 10 μm, composites made with these materials can exhibit a phenomenon called fiber print-through during thermal cycling or actuation. A new class of carbon fibers, multi-walled and single-walled nanotubes, is emerging as a potentially viable material for use in space-based mirrors. Single-walled nanotubes have, potentially, the highest stiffness, strength, and thermal conductivity of any known material. They are only a few nanometers in diameter and can be made with a large aspect ratio (Fig 17). However, at this time, production quantities are very low and prices are very high. Multi-walled nanotubes (or nanofibers) are commercially available in large quantities. They can have diameters as low as 100 nm with large aspect ratios. Their properties are excellent (typical properties - tensile modulus = 600 GPa, tensile strength = 7.0 GPa, CTE = -1.0 ppm/C, and thermal conductivity = 1950 W/m °C) [Ref. 29]. At this time, polymer composites made with these materials have yet to achieve the properties expected given the properties of the fibers. It is believed to be a matter of time before processing issues are solved.

Fig. 17. Carbon nano tubes.

An exciting new material with potential applications to space-based mirrors is carbon foam. There are a variety of manufacturers with a range of carbon foam products. These foams can be tailored (density and morphology) to some degree during manufacturing to display moderate stiffness, moderate compressive strength, low density, low CTE, low or high thermal conductivity, and high or low electrical resistivity. They typically show in-plane isotropy on a plane perpendicular to the foaming direction [Ref. 30]. Relevant properties for a typical 0.55 g/cm^3 graphite foam from Poco Graphite is $-0.65 \text{ ppm/}^\circ\text{C}$ CTE, in-plane thermal conductivity of $45 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$, out-of-plane thermal conductivity of $135 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$, and an out-of-plane compressive strength of 3.0 MPa [Ref. 31]. A 0.45 g/cm^3 density foam from Touchstone Research Laboratory exhibited an out-of-plane modulus of 329 MPa and compressive strength of 3.9 MPa with an in-plane modulus of 1060 MPa and compressive strength of 9.6 MPa [Ref.30]. Research is currently underway to engineer a better microstructure to improve the strengths (compressive, tensile, and shear) of these foams. Additionally, work is ongoing to identify methods for closing off the porous surfaces, adding a polishable substrate, strengthen attachment locations, and protecting the entire surfaces from atomic oxygen. Possible solutions to this problem include functionally grading, the addition of a facesheet material to cover up the pores or add a cladding material to fill up the surface pores. Figure 18 shows examples of carbon foam, one with facesheets of ordinary composite laminate with a topcoat of multi-walled nanofiber/epoxy. Hybrid mirror designs using low CTE glass sols as the close-off and optical substrate material are also being considered.

Fig. 18. a) Carbon foam. b) Carbon foam sandwich with ordinary composite laminate face-sheets top-coated with a layer of multi-walled nanofibers embedded in a polymer matrix.

3.7 Polymer Mirrors:

Space-based mirror systems manufactured with pure polymers will likely take the form of a membrane or inflatable structure rather than a rigid or semi-rigid structure. The potential for very large monolithic aperture mirrors that can be launched and deployed exists with these configurations. An excellent reference concerning the state-of-the-art research into this area is by Jenkins [Ref. 32]. Many significant issues must be addressed before membrane mirrors become a realistic option for space mirrors. The long-term stability of the polymer under space conditions is a question. However, several candidate materials (e.g. Polyimide-based resins) exist and have proven to be robust in the space environment. Coating of a membrane to give it adequate reflectance is a challenge. Many coating techniques impart residual stress into the coating that, especially in the membrane case, will cause warping of the optical figure. Research being conducted by AFLR/ML has demonstrated, on a small scale, the control of residual stress in coatings through the use of pulsed laser deposition. This research has shown that a whole range of residual stress values can be induced into the coating material through control of deposition parameters. Two other major issues with polymer membrane mirrors exist; manufacture of the near net-shape optic and control of the figure.

Several approaches to manufacturing the polymer membrane to net-shape have been proposed. Some of these methods are inflation of a polymer bubble and subsequent sectioning of the relevant portion, spin casting a resin onto a polished mandrel, spin casting a polymer onto a spinning liquid mandrel (called float spin casting) [Ref. 33] and building up a membrane on a polished mandrel using electrospun polymer nanofibers. Work at the AFRL Directed Energy Directorate (AFRL/DE) has resulted in the manufacture of a 280 mm diameter, $20 \mu\text{m}$ thick membrane flat to $<0.25\lambda \text{ RMS}$ and $<2.0\lambda \text{ PV}$ [Ref. 34]. This membrane

was manufactured by spin casting a resin onto a mandrel. The resin was then coated with aluminum and mounted in a stretching frame for testing [Ref. 34]. As shown by these results, it is possible to produce membrane mirrors with relatively good global surface figures. However, these tests were conducted on membranes stretched on rigid frames. To maintain global figure on orbit an aspheric membrane mirror system will probably need some sort of active figure control/ modification mechanism. It is unlikely that the net-shape of the membrane will hold true even with extremely careful design of the frame structure. Recent research at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) and AFRL/ML has demonstrated a 150 mm diameter membrane system with active piezoelectric control [Ref. 35]. The membrane mirrors were constructed by first stretching and adhering a piezoelectric polymer (PVDF) membrane over a rigid aluminum frame. Then, in a process similar to that described in [Ref. 36], multiple layers of a another resin system (RTV silicone rubber) were poured over the taugth PVDF, allowing each previous layer to cure before application of the next layer. This multi-layering approach compensates for any surface irregularities in the non-optically flat PVDF membrane. Before application of the silicone rubber layers, the PVDF layer was etched with a control pattern. Two mirrors were constructed in this manner, each with a different control pattern. Figure 19 shows the control pattern on the backside of one of the mirrors. This mirror was not particularly flat (3.95λ PV, 0.63λ RMS - $\lambda = 632.8\text{nm}$), but was testable in a WaveScope Shack-Hartmann test apparatus. A plot of the Zernike polynomials of this mirror when 3 zones (1,3, and 5) were activated with -600V and the reference configuration subtracted is shown in Figure 20. The resulting induced deformation was 4.43λ PV. Although none of the resin systems used in this research are space qualified, it demonstrates the potential control authority of a distributed array of piezoelectric actuators. It may be possible through multiple layer etching techniques to construct electrode patterns governing different scales of figure control, thus enabling complete figure control of the membrane optic from local to global scales.

Fig. 19. Electrode control pattern etched onto the PVDF membrane of one of the AFIT mirrors.

Fig. 20 : Zernike polynomials resulting from the actuation of electrodes 1, 3, and 5 to -600V .

3.8 Fiber-Reinforced Organic Matrix Composite Mirrors:

Organic matrix composites made with conventional carbon fibers have been considered for use in space-based mirrors for quite some time. They exhibit many properties that are extraordinarily good for mirror systems. They have a high specific stiffness. Depending on fiber choice, they can have good in-plane thermal conductivity. And, most importantly, carbon fiber composites can be designed with near zero CTE for a space-based mirror. Many problems, however, exist with using these materials for mirrors. Polymer resin systems can be sensitive to a variety of environmental factors that put into question their long-term stability. Highly uniform and consistent raw materials (composite prepreg - uncured fiber/matrix sheets) can be difficult to achieve. Finally, the multiphase nature of the composite causes a fiber-print-through phenomenon to deleteriously affect the surface finish of the optic. Many of these problems have good potential solutions that will be discussed, in brief, in the following sections. For a detailed discussion of the use of carbon fiber reinforced composites for PMC mirrors the articles by Connell and Abusafieh [Ref. 37-39] are excellent resource. A large PMC mirror from COI is shown in (Fig 21).

Fig 21. A 2 m PMC mirror produced for NASA Goddard by COI Inc with an areal density of 10kg/m^2 and a figure of 2.3 microns RMS.

A brief comparison of properties between glasses used for mirror systems (ULE, Zerodur, and Pyrex) and a typical polymer matrix composite show the promise of carbon fiber composites. In-plane modulus of elasticity is higher for a quasi-isotropic composite (ranging from 90 GPa to 160 GPa) than for the glasses (ULE=67 GPa, Zerodur=91 GPa, Pyrex=60 GPa). Density of the composite is lower for the composite (1.8 g/cm^3) than for the glasses (ULE= 2.2 g/cm^3 , Zerodur= 2.53 g/cm^3 , Pyrex= 2.23 g/cm^3) [Ref. 40]. In-plane thermal conductivity of a typical quasi-isotropic carbon fiber composites can range from $35\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$ to over $200\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$ (depending on fiber selection) with out-of-plane thermal conductivities in the range of $1\text{-}5\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$ [Ref. 41]. The typical glasses have thermal conductivities of approximately $1.30\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$, $1.57\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$, and $1.17\text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$ for ULE, Zerodur, and Pyrex, respectively [Ref. 40]. ULE and Zerodur have fantastic CTEs of $0.03\text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ and $0.05\text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ at room temperatures [Ref. 40]. Composites can be tailored to have as low as $\pm 0.01\text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ in-plane CTE over a small temperature range [Ref. 39]. Additionally, at a very broad temperature range, the composite can be tailored to have a $\pm 0.10\text{ ppm}^\circ\text{C}$ in-plane CTE [Ref. 39].

Two of the major issues with the use of polymer matrix composite material for space-based optics, uniformity/consistency of the raw materials and environmental stability of the composite, have essentially been solved. If great care is used in the manufacture of the lamina prepreg (the uncured single plies used to build up a laminate) the uniformity and consistency can be dramatically improved. This has been demonstrated by Abusafieh [Ref. 38, 39] on

graphite/cyanate-ester composites. Moisture absorption and microcracking have been the major environmental concern with polymeric composite materials. Toughened epoxies have helped solve the toughness issue, but have not addressed the moisture absorption. Cyanate ester resin systems show the most promise at this time to solve environmental stability issues. They have low moisture absorption and resist microcracking. They also have negligible cure shrinkage, a feature that will help reduce residual stresses that may cause mirror warpage.

Fiber print-through is caused by a mismatch in properties between the fibers and the resin matrix binding them together. The resin will shrink upon cure while the fibers do not change shape. Also, polymer resins generally have very high CTEs compared with the negative CTE of carbon fibers. These resin systems are generally cured at elevated temperatures with respect to their intended operational temperature. This mismatch in CTEs results, upon cool down, in a larger dimensional change in the resin than in the fibers. Also, polymer resins generally exhibit a dimensional change upon absorption of water (coefficient of moisture expansion CME) while the carbon fibers do not change dimension. The resin shrinkage and CTE/CME mismatch combine to form valleys in the resin-rich zones between adjacent fibers, resulting in significant surface roughness. This fiber print-through phenomenon affects a composite mirror whether it was polished or replicated except in the case where the use temperature is exactly the same as the manufacturing/or polishing temperature.

There are several viable solutions to this problem. One method involves applying a thin layer of homogeneous material (polymer resin or glassy sol-gel) between the composite and the mirror surface. This extra layer is thick relative to the fiber diameters and fiber spacing, but thin relative to the overall structure. It serves to damp out the effects of shrinkage and CTE/CME mismatch. An extra layer of resin has been demonstrated to produce surface roughness on the order 20 angstroms RMS in replicated optics [Ref. 37]. A polished overcoat of a glassy sol-gel layer has been demonstrated with a 30 angstrom RMS surface roughness [Ref. 37].

Another possible solution to the fiber print-through problem could involve modifying the resin system or fibers in the layers of the composite nearest the surface. Smaller diameter fibers, such as multi-walled and/or single-walled carbon nanotubes, could reduce the surface roughness by reducing the spatial distance between fibers. These nano fibers or other nano-additives (clays, ceramic particles, etc.) could also be used to modify the resin properties to reduce cure shrinkage, CTE, and/or CME to more closely match the fiber properties.

3.7 Glass/Ceramic Syntactic Foams:

Composite materials made from glass, ceramic, or polymer microballoons with polymer resin matrices, broadly known as syntactic foams, are showing very promising characteristics suitable for space-based mirror systems. They are essentially a highly filled polymer system where the fill material is made up of very small (2-100 μm diameter) hollow spheres of another material. Ceramic and glass microballoons are of special interest for use in mirror systems. These types of microballoons can have very low CTE and are relatively stiff compared with their bulk densities. Syntactic foams typically have low densities (0.2 g/cm^3 to 0.9 g/cm^3). They are commercially available in cured and uncured forms with a variety of constituent materials. Specialized manufacturing procedures described by Karst [Ref. 43] have optimized the packing of glass microspheres resulting in very consistent syntactic foams with 0.55 g/cm^3 density and very high compressive strengths (67.4 MPa versus 30 MPa for other manufacturers). Foams similar to those described by Karst but made using a cyanate ester resin system have been shown to have a CTE of 8.1 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ (0.7 g/cm^3 density) while syntactic foams made using ceramic microballoons where made with a 5.0 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ CTE (0.9 g/cm^3 density) [Ref. 44].

Most advertised syntactic foams are essentially nonporous. All interstitial spaces between microballoons are filled with resin. A significant portion of the density of the composite is made up of resin. In the case of the foams by Karst [Ref. 43], the true particle density of the microballoons was 0.25 g/cm^3 while the finished composite was 0.55 g/cm^3 , an increase of 0.2 g/cm^3 . For a low density, lightly loaded mirror the only purpose of the resin in the composite is to serve as a binder of sufficient structural integrity for the expected mechanical and thermal load. Any more resin will increase the density and will likely increase the CTE/CME and cure shrinkage of the composite as a whole. Recent research at the Air Force Research Laboratory Materials and Manufacturing Directorate (AFRL/ML) has developed a methodology to produce syntactic foam composites with very low resin content. Specifically, 2 versions of the composites were manufactured. Both used 3M ScotchLite H20/1000 microballoons and Epon 828 resin. The composites were made with 15% and 5% by volume resin, respectively. The resulting composites had densities of 0.25 g/cm^3 for the 15% resin volume syntactic and 0.21 g/cm^3 for the 5% resin volume syntactic. The 5% resin foam approached the microsphere true particle density of 0.20 g/cm^3 . It displayed reasonable compression strength of 2.5 MPa. A preliminary moiré interferometry study at AFRL/ML has shown that the average cure-shrinkage of the material is approximately 0.1%, much lower than the approximately 1-2% of resin itself. CTE measurements have shown the average CTE of the 5% resin content foam to be 9.6 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ and the 15% resin foam to be 13.8 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$. Note that the glass microballoons have an inherent CTE of 8.36 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$ [Ref. 45] and the Epon 828 has a CTE of 57.2

$\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$. Small replicated mirrors produced at AFRL/ML using syntactic foams are shown in Figure 22. It is believed that improvements to the process will improve upon these already low cure shrinkage and CTE values. The near zero CTE sols and microballoons that are being produced by MSNW Inc for AFRL/ML and this should greatly reduce the overall CTE value of these types of foam composites.

Fig. 22. a) Replicated syntactic foam mirror
b) Molded rib-structure for reducing part weight.

3.8 Nano-technology—What can it do for large space-based mirrors?

If one reviews the section on monolithic glass mirrors, one will see Zerodur made by Schott Glass, the near zero CTE of this glass is produced by the homogenous nucleation and growth of a negative CTE crystalline phase in a positive CTE glass matrix. Many material exist which show negative CTE behavior and if these can be dispersed homogeneously in a positive CTE matrix then the CTE of the composite material can be reduced to near zero values, as seen in all the composite mirror structures. Recent work at AFRL/MLN is focused on producing nanometer sized, negative CTE powders utilizing various processing techniques. Incorporating these nano powders into polymer, metal, and ceramic matrices to produce near zero CTE matrix materials that are polishable to visual quality (<100nm, or one-fifth the wavelength of light). One such material is zirconium tungstate (ZrW_2O_8), which has a complex cube crystal structure (isotropic behavior) and a negative coefficient of thermal expansion (approximately -5.7 $\text{ppm}/^\circ\text{C}$). It has recently been synthesized to about 300-nanometer particle size and has successfully been mixed with glass to produce near zero CTE behavior (Fig 22).

Fig. 23. CTE behavior of ZrW_2O_8 / glass CMC.

These powders were also dispersed in both a thermoset and thermoplastic polymer. Unfortunately, debonding occurred at the powder-polymer interface resulting in no change in CTE of the composite. Surface treatments for the powders are being investigated that will allow for stronger interfacial bonding in the polymer case. Several other chemistries of mixed oxides have also been identified in the literature that have more negative CTEs than ZrW_2O_8 . However, these compounds are hygroscopic in nature. Alloying of these compounds may eliminate this problem.

Another place where nano-materials may help the mirror community is in replication technology [Ref 46]. Metallic nano-laminate foils have been produced with enough tensile strength that they can be removed from a mandrel and handled like a large contact lens. If handling doesn't introduce permanent deformation, then they could be positioned and bonded onto machined structural substrates, possibly eliminating the polishing steps. Alternatively, they could be left on the mandrel and the structural substrate bonded to them. After bonding the whole system could be removed from the mandrel. There are many critical issues that have to be resolved to make either of these concepts viable:

1. Can nano-laminates be fabricated that match the low CTE's of the structural substrates?
2. Will a nanolaminate need to be stiffened prior to bonding?
3. What kind of material can we use for bonding agent and can we make it so it doesn't shrink or pick up moisture?
4. Will we have to have different bonding agents for cryo, ambient, and laser applications?

5. Can we get by with machining the structural substrate instead of polishing it? Will we get print through problems?
6. How many times can we use a mandrel before having to re-polish it?

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

The state-of-the-art material of choice for mirrors is monolithic glass, owing to the ease of fabricating with high precision on curvature, with roughness amplitudes much less than wavelength of light and very low distortions arising from thermal fluctuations due to low thermal expansion. The AMSD program has shown that monolithic glass mirror designs can be lightweighted to around 15kg/m^2 and its cost reduced substantially compared to Hubble based technology. However, it is felt that the current lightweighted glass technology is fast approaching its limit and that any further substantial reductions in the areal density would require hybrid and/or composite mirror designs. Composite designs are favored since they also provide robustness and durability to the mirror system through their increased strength, modulus and fracture toughness. It is anticipated that an order of magnitude increase in fracture toughness, compared to monolithic glass, will be required in large segmented mirror designs for unshielded space-based applications. The high fracture toughness is desired to avoid catastrophic mirror failure due to assembly accidents and micrometeoroid impact damage.

The future needs of the Air Force and the Department of Defense will also require reductions in lead times, processing costs, and launch load/weights. New materials and processing methods are needed. Mirror structural substrates made out of advanced composite materials (metal, ceramic, and polymer), foams, and microsphere arrays do allow for CTE and modulus tailorability, low-density, and high strength, stiffness, and toughness. Small size mirror structural substrates have been fabricated from these new emerging materials but scaling to 2 or 3 meter segments will require new resources both time and funding. Producing the surface finish and figure requirements needed for visible quality optics from these multi-phase complex systems will be difficult. New methods of polishing, replication, and sol-gel or polymer spinning will be required to produce quality optical substrate. Finally, research will be required to produce uniform stress free reflective coatings and dielectric stacks on such large mirror systems.

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